

Agile Piloting for Greener Cities

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Abstract

As climate change intensifies, cities face growing pressure to adopt nature-based solutions that enhance urban resilience. However, densifying urban environments often lack space for traditional greenery, requiring innovative approaches. Agile piloting programs offer a powerful tool to co-create and test green infrastructure solutions in real-world settings. Forum Virium Helsinki has implemented this model to support the development of green infrastructure solutions, such as green walls, green roofs, and supporting digital solutions. This paper presents the methodology, outcomes, and insights gained from recent urban greenery pilots in Helsinki. Findings indicate that multi-actor coordination requires resources, even small-scale solutions benefit biodiversity, and digital tools are needed to enable scalable, measurable green infrastructure.

Key words

Green infrastructure, Agile piloting, Urban resilience, Nature-based solutions, Living labs.

Problem Statement

Urban areas are simultaneously densifying and facing the impacts of climate change—heat waves, flooding, and biodiversity loss. While green infrastructure is recognised as an effective mitigation and adaptation tool (e.g., Demuzere et al., 2014), limited space in dense cities restricts its implementation. There is an urgent need for fast, adaptive methods to test and scale new greening solutions.

Methods

Forum Virium Helsinki, the City of Helsinki’s innovation company, has applied Agile piloting to support green infrastructure innovation. The novelty of this method lies in its application to a field typically dominated by slow, traditional procurement processes. Piloting programs follow a structured process:

1. Identifying challenges with city stakeholders.
2. Launching an open call for tenders targeting startups and SMEs.
3. Selecting solutions based on innovativeness, feasibility, impact, and co-creation potential.
4. Implementing real-life pilots with support for testing and evaluation (Mustonen et al. 2018).

Rooted in Living Lab principles, this approach facilitates experimentation in real-life settings and fosters stakeholder engagement with direct feedback loops.

Outcomes

Agile pilots in the PilotGreen project 2024–2025 demonstrated the potential of this approach to promote climate-resilient greenery in dense urban environments. Seven solutions were tested, including modular vegetation systems, green walls and roofs, and technologies to assess environmental impact and enable efficient maintenance.

One standout pilot transformed a tram stop with vegetated plant wall pillars utilizing rainwater and modular design. The green tram stops not only proved successful in user surveys, gaining strong public support, but also created direct business opportunities, as the solution is now being scaled to more locations across the city.

Pilot Insights

1. **Multi-actor complexity:** Even a simple intervention like a green tram stop requires coordination between multiple actors, such as the tram line commissioner, planner/constructor, and tram stop manager.
2. **Pollinator highway:** Pilot findings indicate well-designed modular green elements, like green walls and roofs, enhance urban biodiversity by providing steppingstones for pollinators and improving microclimates. (Tala, 2024).
3. **Digital tools enable scaling:** Technologies utilised in the pilots, like remote sensing and environmental DNA analysis allow for resource-efficient maintenance and measurable impact assessment, making solutions more viable and justifiable.

Conclusion

To scale green infrastructure effectively, both public and private landowners should be engaged, with a crucial focus on the entire process from co-design to maintenance. Increased biodiversity targets are driving broader implementation and opening up new business opportunities for startups and SMEs. Agile pilots accelerate learning, inspire new actors, and counterbalance the slow pace of systemic change. Green infrastructure pilots will continue in Helsinki, focusing on benefits like cooling and noise reduction.

This approach has helped institutionalize a more experimental culture within city administrations, particularly in departments responsible for streets and parks. The model's success has also extended beyond Helsinki. During the PilotGreen project, the agile piloting framework for green infrastructure has been transferred to the cities of Lahti and Espoo, demonstrating its scalability to other urban contexts.

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